

UNIVERSAL PRINCIPLES IN THE WORKS OF KADZUO ISHIGURO, AN ENGLISHMAN FROM JAPAN

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Abstract: In the article, the description of universal principles in the life of Kazuo Isiguro, who is considered one of the most influential writers of world literature of the 21st century, and a scientific approach to them using the example of the writer's famous works were presented. Kazuo Isiguro, winner of the 2017 Nobel Prize in Literature, has been described as "a writer who, in his novels of great emotional power, exposes the void beneath our false connection to the world." The article contains quotes from the writer's works.

Keywords: Oceanographer, Principle, Universal, Work, English Literature, Kazuo Isiguro, Nobel Prize, Dull Hills, The Artist of the Floating World, Remains of the Day, Never Let Me Go "Don't Let Go", science fiction.

Kazuo Ishiguro was born on November 8, 1954 in the city of Nagasaki, Japan, in the family of the famous oceanographer Shizuo Ishiguro. When the boy was 5 years old, his father found a good job in his specialty in Great Britain and moved to this country with his family. According to Kazuo Isiguro's childhood memories, in 1960, his father was offered a research job at the National Institute of Oceanography in Surrey, the administrative center of Surrey County, but as fate would have it, this country would become the family's lifelong home. . Kazuo Isiguro attended primary school in Staffon and then grammar school in Surrey. After graduating from school, he will travel to the United States and Canada. In fact, his childhood dream of becoming a musician remained a dream, he did not become a true musician. In 1978, he defended his bachelor's degree in English and philosophy at the University of Kent, and in 1980 he defended his master's thesis at the University of East Anglia. Malcolm Bradbury's class once at the university leaves a special impression on him. He likes to remember many times those lessons that created an endless interest and love for literature. Isiguro became a British citizen in 1983. After graduating from the University of Kent, Isiguro also studied writing at the University of East Anglia (Norwich), and K. Isiguro's first creative work was published in the form of a story in Bananas magazine in 1980. The first novel published in 1982 is the writer's first novel - The dimly visible hills. It was published in 1982. The play is the story of Etsuko, a middle-aged Japanese woman who lives in England and experiences the

suicide of her eldest daughter, Keiko. Etsuko leaves Nagasaki, which is recovering after the nuclear bombing, and moves to a completely foreign world - England. The novel was awarded the Winifred Holtby, Memorial Award for the year's best works published abroad. Isigurō's next novel, *The Artist of the Floating World*, published in 1986, was also a work devoted to Japan and brought Kazuo Isigurō international fame. This book was shortlisted for the Booker Prize and won the Whitbird Prize.

"*The Remains of the Day*", published in 1989, brought Isiguro universal fame and made him a true legend of British literature during his lifetime. The work was recognized as one of the best English novels of the late 20th century. According to British literary experts, the work "*The Remains of the Day*" that attracted more literature lovers can be viewed from different angles. First of all, the image of a national Englishman is analyzed in the image of Stevens, the hero of the work, the chief servant of a noble house. Although some researchers want to reduce to this character the function of the unreliable storyteller, who is an invariable device in all of Isiguro's novels, surprisingly, the character of Stevens is truly a national legend. Together with the described property - the concept of being English. Although country estates are slowly becoming a thing of the past, Stevens remains true to his values. The duty and dignity that the hero thinks with all his mind means that his service to his master must be at the highest level. According to some researchers, this may be a subtle satire of the author on England or humanity. Based on this idea, R. Trimm connects the limitations of Stevens with the moral rules of the nation, in particular with the workers under their command of the big owners, with their way of life and clear but unwritten rules. Another work of Kazuo Isiguro's life, based on universal principles, written in the direction of soft science fiction, is called "*Never Let Me Go*". The main character of the work is Cathy.X. a thirty-year-old clone. Cathy echoes Stephen's concept of dignity in *The Remains of the Day*. The play is set in an alternative English society in the late 1990s, where an evil government sees clones as organ donors.

A great feature of *Never Let Me Go* is the story of Katie's quiet breakup. Kazuo Isiguro describes a boarding school for clones in Hailsham through powerful flashbacks. There, Katie and her friends are preparing for a mysterious, hidden destiny of which they are completely unaware. As they get older, it means that it is time to become a donor. They become donors three or even four times. The fate of the clones ends in death, and unfortunately, this fact is obvious to everyone from the very beginning. And like Cathy, caregivers support the clones until it's their turn to be a donor. Isiguro skillfully portrays Katie and her clone friends as ordinary people. But he also touches on the cruelty in their lives. For example, Katie, like the female

singer of the imaginary pop tune she heard in Hailsham, wants to never let her baby go. This is an impossible dream for Cathy, as all clones are infertile. This desire means that Katie is also human, that she also has a soul, and at the same time, the society is treating her inhumanely. Isiguro also made two original films for television. He is a member of the Royal Literary Society. His works have been translated into more than 30 languages. According to research by Time magazine, his novel "Don't Let Me Go" published in 2005 was among the 100 best novels of all time by English writers. Isiguro was awarded the Booker Prize in 1989, the Order of the British Empire in 1995 and the Order of Arts and Letters in 1998. In 2017, Norwegian academics found him worthy of the Nobel Prize in Literature.

Every work of Kazuo Isiguro has been a sensation in literature. In her best-selling novel, Don't Let Me Go, thirty-year-old Katie recalls the shocking realities, half-baked news, and mysterious dangers she spent at a privileged school in Hailsham. He feels like he was in that time, he tells the story as if he had returned to those realities. The work is not just a love story or an expression of friendship and memories, it is a "certain level of materialization of the philosophy of giving your life." This work is a novel-story about the heart-wrenching events of the present and the past. Pain has its cure, but after reading the work, it will stay with you for a long time.

Research results:

When Kazuo Isiguro's novel "Never Let Me Go" came out, many people called it a terrible futurological prediction. However, the writer himself noted that the work is not a quotation, it is just life, the life of an ordinary person, there is no pretense in it. He said in one of his interviews: We convince ourselves that there will be no progress and development without freedom, but we flourished even during the period of Chinese captivity! We don't think so, how many people in Asia are making a living, even if it is with someone's help?! In fact, in Kazuo Isiguro's works, one can understand universal principles in the form of characters and the time and space that surrounds them at the same time. Any artistic work is, first of all, an expression of the personality of the person who wrote it, both from the point of view of a set of ideas, and at the level of their linguistic and methodological implementation. Even as the great German philosopher Johann Wolfgang Goethe pointed out, every writer, whether he wants it or not, portrays himself in a certain way in his works. This means that by describing a certain part of life, the writer thereby demonstrates his attitude, the style of his thoughts and feelings. The works of Kazuo Isiguro and the characters in them are among us. We are all familiar with the universal human feelings and

worldview embodied in them. Kazuo Isiguro's greatest achievement is that he penned these principles and continues to convey them to the reader.

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